

**Merging of ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat altimeter data
over the Greenland ice sheet**

Technical Report

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Abstract

Greenland ice sheet elevation changes for 16.5-year time period from 1992 to 2008 were analyzed from ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat satellite radar altimeter data. Development of the method for determination inter-satellite biases was performed for merging radar altimeter measurements from different satellites and creating continuous time series. Inter-satellite biases for elevation and backscattered coefficient have shown to be significantly effected by the bias between measurements in ascending and descending orbits. Adjusting elevation time series for correlation between elevation and backscattered power changes over Greenland ice sheet significantly lowered elevation change rate estimates and resulted in consistency between radar and laser altimeter results. Detailed analysis of this correction revealed its essential dependence on temporal variations of the correlation gradient between elevation and backscattered power in addition to variations of backscattered power. As the correction represents changes in scattering characteristics of the ice sheet, its applying is likely able to correct elevation change estimates for penetration of part of the radar altimeter signal through the surface. Over 76% of Greenland ice sheet area elevation change rate of 0.8 ± 0.3 cm/year from 1992 to 2008 was found. Increases in surface elevation, which were observed over the high-elevation regions of Greenland from 1995 have decelerated over the period from 2003 to 2005 and changed to elevation decrease during 2006-2008. For the whole period 1992-2008 elevation increase is 1.8 ± 0.2 cm/year over 87% of the areas above 1500 m. In contrast, over 38% of the low-elevation areas below 1500 m rate of elevation change is -7.1 ± 1.1 cm/year and surface-elevation decreases that started from 2000 have continued.

1. Introduction

The Greenland Ice Sheet is an important earth-system component whose potential melting is critical for sea-level change and freshwater impact on ocean circulation. The mass balance of the Greenland ice sheet remains uncertain, although improvements in measurements from satellite sensors can reduce this uncertainty [e.g. Alley et al., 2007]. Satellite altimetry is a precise method that produces sufficient spatial coverage and density of the measurements needed to perform the study of the Greenland Ice Sheet [Khvorostovsky et al., 2003; Johannessen et al. 2005; Zwally, 2005]. Satellite altimeter measurements of ice-sheet surface elevation allow us to determine directly the changes in ice volume including temporal variability and spatial distribution. Surface elevation

changes represent mainly variations in snow accumulation, melting and ice flow velocity, and can be converted to mass balance using average density of the firn/ice column. Thus, analysis of long-term surface elevation time series of Greenland Ice Sheet is important for study its current state, inter- and intra-annual mass balance changes.

Measurements of radar altimeters from series of satellites (ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat) allow investigation the surface elevation changes of the whole Greenland ice sheet from 1992. Methodology on merging of radar altimeter measurements from different satellites through estimation and using inter-satellite biases was developed and applied to create continuous elevation time series. In addition biases between backscattered power measurements were calculated to create their time series along with time series of surface elevation for determining correction, which accounts correlation between these two parameters [Wingham et al., 1998, Zwally et al., 2005, Davis and Ferguson, 2004].

2. Elevation and backscattered power biases

Commonly used method for ice sheet elevation change study is a crossover analysis using differences in elevation over the location where two orbit passes – ascending and descending – cross each other. Spatially variant inter-satellite bias between surface elevation measurements from ERS-1 and ERS-2 satellites was taken into account for Greenland ice sheet elevation change estimation through applying different techniques [Johannessen et al., 2005, Zwally et al., 2005]. Determination of inter-satellite biases between measurements of any two satellites allow to use much larger amount of crossover point then only crossover differences between measurements from the same satellite. For example, if for both satellites number of ascending and descending orbit passes is equal, then number of inter-satellite crossovers is $2\sqrt{N_{cr1}}\sqrt{N_{cr2}}$, where N_{cr1} and N_{cr2} are amounts of crossovers formed only from orbit passes of one and another satellite respectively. When using measurements from series of satellites, in the case if all of them has equal total number of orbit passes used in the analysis, total amount of crossovers is amounted to $N_{cr} \cdot N_{Sat}^2$, where N_{cr} – number of crossovers formed using orbit passes of single satellite, N_{Sat} – number of satellites, i.e. including inter-satellite crossovers in the analysis increases their total amount by factor N_{Sat} . Furthermore applying inter-satellite biases allow creating continuous time series for the long time period directly from all available crossovers when measurements from series of satellites are used.

We used ERS-1 and ERS-2 ice-mode measurements and Envisat fine-mode measurements, which cover approximately the same area of Greenland Ice Sheet [Brenner et al, 2007], with applied

the same corrections for range measurement as were used in [Johannessen et al., 2005] to create 3-months averaged elevation time series over grid cells 1° longitude \times 0.5° latitude.

Figure 1. Variations of backscattered power parameters (backscatter coefficient and AGC) for the area $79\text{-}79.5^\circ\text{N}$ and $44\text{-}45^\circ\text{W}$

Although discontinuity of backscatter power measured by radar altimeters from ERS-1 and ERS-2 satellites was noted in [Brenner et al., 2000], distribution and mean values of backscatter power biases, and their applying for ice sheet elevation change calculation have not been reported. Fig. 1 shows example of variations of backscattered power parameters – backscatter coefficient (σ^0) and Automatic Gain Control (AGC) – measured by radar altimeters from ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat satellites. Although σ^0 is a calibrated and therefore more accurate estimation of backscattered pulse return power, while AGC is used for its calculation, [e.g. Davis et al., 2001, http://envisat.esa.int/pub/ESA_DOC/ENVISAT/RA2-MWR/PH_light_1rev2_ESA.pdf], both these parameters were used to determine correction for relationship between changes in elevation and backscattered power [Wingham et al., 1998, Davis and Ferguson, 2004, Zwally et al., 2005]. It is clearly seen that there is inconsistency in backscatter power measurements between different satellite altimeters and between σ^0 estimations before and after August 1993 for ERS-1. Thus to accounts correlation between elevation and backscattered power biases for both of these parameters should be determined and applied.

2.1 Inter-satellite biases of elevation and backscattered power

Because the biases between altimeter measurements are spatially variable they should be estimated with the same spatial resolution as used for forming time series of elevation and backscattered power, i.e. for the individual grid cells. The most reasonable method for determination of inter-satellite ERS-1/ERS-2 and ERS-2/Envisat biases is to average crossover differences with small (e.g. < 30 days) time intervals between measurements from different satellites. Such crossovers are available during the periods of simultaneous operation of ERS-1 and -2 altimeters from May 1995 to May 1996, and ERS-2 and Envisat altimeters from October 2002 to June 2003. However this method of averaging (MA) cannot be applied for large amount of grid cells over Greenland, because quantity of such crossovers is not sufficient to calculate statistically significant results. It is especially remarkable for southern part of Greenland, where poor density of altimeter measurement is observed, and for determination of ERS-2/Envisat biases because of short, only 9 months, temporal overlapping. In [Zwally et al., 2005] smoothed assessments of ERS-1/ERS-2 elevation biases were estimated by averaging crossover differences through using crossovers located within 400 km areas and a restriction to elevations within 250m centered in 50 km grids. However this assessment does not reflect grid scale features of the bias, which may vary remarkably from cell to cell, even over flat areas of the Greenland ice sheet.

In order to obtain the assessments of the bias within each grid point Johannessen et al., [2005] applied the technique based on dH/dt -method using linear regression fit of inter-satellite elevation crossover differences (dH) to corresponding time differences (dt) for calculation of ERS-1/ERS-2 elevation bias. Applying this method of regression (MR) biases were estimated as an offset of the linear fit from the origin at the point where $dt=0$. This method gave higher reliability of the results through using large number of crossovers formed using measurements from 1992 to 1996 and from 1995 to 1999 for ERS-1 and ERS-2 altimeters respectively. However this method accounts only linear trend of elevation change over the time period, which was used for bias calculations. In order to take into account temporal variations we applied MR using polynomial fit for crossovers with possibly small dt . As well as when using linear fit elevation biases were calculated as offset of the fit from the origin at the point where $dt=0$, i.e. as an absolute term c_1 in the polynomial fit equation:

$$dH = c_1 + c_2dt + c_3dt^2 + \dots + c_ndt^{n-1}.$$

The similar method was applied also for estimating of backscattered power biases. The largest dt , which reflect the amount of crossovers involved in calculations, and order of polynomial fit used for assessment of the biases were determined from the following algorithm.

In order to use the possibly smallest values of dt the biases were initially calculated from crossovers with $dt < 30$ days. If amount of crossovers is not sufficient to obtain statistically significant result then the range of dt was extended with the 30 days step, i.e. to 60 days, 90 days, 120 days etc. Criteria used to determine significance of the result are the following.

- With increasing of the order of polynomial fit the estimated bias should converge. It means that difference between biases calculated using, for example, second and third orders of polynomial fit should be less then difference between biases calculated using first and second orders. If this difference is less then 2 % or less then 2 cm for elevation and 0.1 dB for backscattered power, then the estimated value is considered as assessment of the bias. This criterion of convergence was applied because estimates of the bias using higher order of polynomial fit should better take into account temporal variation of crossover differences in case if amount of crossover is sufficient and crossover differences are randomly distributed.
- The bias estimates and regression equation calculated using all orders of polynomial fit (from the first to the highest, which were used for bias assessment) should be statistically significant above 0.05 significance level, if using t-test and F-test.

To remove outliers similar to iterative two standard deviation editing procedure was applied to crossover differences for all bias estimations using the following criteria (for elevations):

$$|dH_i - dH_{i,fit}| > 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{rss}{n}}$$

where dH_i and $dH_{i,fit}$ – values of actual elevation crossover difference and estimated from polynomial fit, rss - residual sum of squares, n – number of crossovers. Similar criterion was also used for backscattered power calculations.

In order to take into account ascending/descending bias [Legressy et al., 1999, Arthern et al., 2001] we found two estimates for each of ERS-1/ERS-2 and ERS-2/Envisat biases of elevation and backscattered power using two different sets of crossover differences. One set of crossovers was obtained using differences between measurements in ascending orbits (A) from one satellite and measurements in descending orbits (D) from another one, and vice versa for the second set:

$$AD_{ers2-ers1} = A_{ers2} - D_{ers1},$$

$$DA_{ers2-ers1} = D_{ers2} - A_{ers1},$$

$$AD_{env-ers2} = A_{env} - D_{ers2},$$

$$DA_{env-ers2} = D_{env} - A_{ers2},$$

where $AD_{ers2-ers1}$, $DA_{ers2-ers1}$, $AD_{env-ers2}$ and $DA_{env-ers2}$ – elevation and backscattered power crossover differences between measurements from ERS-1 and ERS-2, and ERS-2 and Envisat satellites. Then two estimates of each bias – $B_{ers2 a - ers1 d}$, $B_{ers2 d - ers1 a}$, $B_{env a - ers2 d}$ and $B_{env d - ers2 a}$ – were applied to corresponding inter-satellite crossovers. Thus, in addition to estimation of the biases with higher

spatial resolution, involving large amount of crossover point allows to take into account ascending/descending biases.

Before calculation of inter-satellite elevation biases spatially invariant offsets between measurements from different satellites were applied to elevation crossover differences in order to reveal spatially-variant biases influenced only by interaction of altimeter signal and ice sheet surface. When calculating ERS-1/ERS-2 biases ERS-1 elevation measurements were lowered by 40.9 cm [Femenias, 1997, Brenner et al., 2000], while Envisat measurements were increased by 73.68 cm [e.g. Roca et al., 2003, Shum et al., 2003] before estimating ERS-2/Envisat elevation bias.

When calculating inter-satellite biases the existence of crossovers with dt close to 0 is critical for both – MA and MR – methods. Since ERS-1 and Envisat do not have period of simultaneous operation these methods are not appropriate for estimating ERS-1/Envisat biases, which should be applied, if using ERS-1/Envisat crossovers for forming continuous time series. Therefore ERS-1/Envisat biases were estimated as a sum of two other determined biases (ERS-1/ERS-2 and ERS-2/ Envisat) and ascending/descending bias of ERS-2 measurements $B_{ers2 d - ers2 a}$:

$$B_{env a - ers1 d} = B_{ers2 a - ers1 d} + B_{env a - ere2 d} + B_{ers2 d - ers2 a}$$

$$B_{env d - ere1 a} = B_{ers2 d - ere1 a} + B_{env d - ere2 a} - B_{ers2 d - ers2 a}$$

$B_{ers2 d - ers2 a}$ was calculated from $DA_{ers2-ers2} = D_{ers2} - A_{ers2}$ crossover differences in a similar way as ERS-1/ERS-2 and ERS-2/Envisat biases.

Comparison of biases calculated by MR and conventional MA for the cells, where number of crossovers with $dt < 30$ days is sufficient to obtain significant results ($s < 0.05$), indicates good agreement between the results with correlation coefficient ranging for different biases from 0.87 to 0.95. At the same time criterion of convergence applied in MR in many cases results in estimation of the biases using dt larger then 30 days, even if conventional MA gives statistically significant results. Therefore, when creating time series, we applied, if available, biases obtained by MA, and biases obtained by MR in other cases. For different elevation and σ^0 biases MR was applied over 17 to 50% of the area, where biases could be estimated (Table 1 and 2), indicating significant contribution from both – MA and MR – methods. However obtaining of all biases within individual cell by MA was possible only over $324.6 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ (244 cells) or 24.5% of the area, where elevation and σ^0 time series were formed (Fig. 2k). Average range of dt used for calculating of the biases (Table 1 and 2) is primarily depends on area, where MA was applied, which in turn resulted from amount of crossovers available over individual cell. Therefore the least values of dt range are observed in the central and northern areas of Greenland. Also range of dt used for estimation of elevation biases is larger then for σ^0 because of higher spatial variability of surface elevation.

Dataset	Biases over the area, where they are available					Biases over the same area (1194.9*10 ³ km ² , 768 cells)		
	Elevation bias, cm	Cells	Area, *10 ³ km ²	dt range, days	MR area, %	Elevation bias, cm	dt range, days	MR area, %
$B_{ers2 d - ers1 a}$	48.9 ± 1.9	836	1318.5	261 ± 16	32	46.6 ± 1.6	205 ± 15	27
$B_{ers2 a - ers1 d}$	15.7 ± 2.0	824	1294.6	345 ± 18	50	12.5 ± 1.8	320 ± 17	48
$B_{env d - ers2 a}$	70.5 ± 1.9	866	1378.8	275 ± 16	32	67.8 ± 1.8	201 ± 14	25
$B_{env a - ers2 d}$	51.9 ± 2.1	875	1392.5	263 ± 15	34	44.4 ± 1.9	207 ± 14	30
$B_{ers2 d - ers2 a}$	19.9 ± 1.6	933	1507.6	123 ± 10	18	18.9 ± 1.3	55 ± 5	9

Table 1. Inter-satellite and ERS-2 ascending/descending elevation biases averaged over areas with cells, where biases could be estimated. *dt* range is the average range of time differences used for bias calculation, MR area – area, where bias was estimated by the method of regression, in percents of the whole area, where bias was obtained.

Dataset	Biases over the area, where they are available					Biases over the same area (1284.9*10 ³ km ² , 816 cells)		
	σ^0 bias, dB	Cells	Area, *10 ³ km ²	dt range, days	MR area, %	σ^0 bias, dB	dt range, days	MR area, %
$B_{ers2 d - ers1 a}$	-7.49 ± 0.02	850	1341.1	133 ± 11	20	-7.48 ± 0.02	111 ± 9	17
$B_{ers2 a - ers1 d}$	-7.31 ± 0.02	852	1344.7	110 ± 9	19	-7.32 ± 0.02	96 ± 9	16
$B_{env d - ers2 a}$	-3.89 ± 0.03	867	1385.8	173 ± 12	25	-3.85 ± 0.03	142 ± 12	20
$B_{env a - ers2 d}$	-3.91 ± 0.03	868	1384.3	138 ± 11	17	-3.81 ± 0.03	105 ± 10	12
$B_{ers2 d - ers2 a}$	0.05 ± 0.02	925	1495.0	137 ± 9	34	-0.03 ± 0.02	88 ± 7	27

Table 2. Same as Table 1, but for backscatter coefficient biases.

Distribution of calculated ERS-1/ERS-2, ERS-2/Envisat and ERS-2 ascending/descending biases (Fig. 2a-j) shows significant spatial variability and the features of different scales for both – elevation and σ^0 . The main feature of elevation inter-satellite biases (Fig. 2a-d) is that the largest and smallest values are observed over margins and central areas respectively. Distributions for corresponding σ^0 biases are more complicated, but also have pronounced large-scale features (Fig. 2f-i). Another essential characteristic of these distributions is a strong influence of ascending/descending bias. Elevation biases $B_{ers2 d - ers1 a}$ and $B_{env d - ers2 a}$ (Fig. 2a and c) are significantly larger than $B_{ers2 a - ers1 d}$ and $B_{env a - ers2 d}$ (Fig. 2b and d) respectively. For σ^0 effect of ascending/descending bias is remarkable for ERS-1/ERS-2 bias distribution (Fig. 2f and g) and over some regions of ERS-2/Envisat one (Fig. 2h and i). Therefore when forming elevation and backscattered power time series all determined biases should be applied separately for corresponding inter-satellite crossovers, and with taken into account ERS-2 ascending/descending biases, when using ERS-1×Envisat crossovers.

- MA only
- MA and MR
- Without taking into account Asc/Dsc bias

Figure 2. Inter-satellite biases for elevation (a) – (e) and σ^0 (f) – (j). (a) and (f) – $B_{ers2 d - ers1 a}$, (b) and (g) – $B_{ers2 a - ers1 d}$, (c) and (h) – $B_{env d - ers2 a}$, (d) and (i) – $B_{env a - ers2 d}$, (e) and (j) – $B_{ers2 d - ers2 a}$. (k) – Distribution of the methods used for estimation of calculated biases: applying only method of averaging (MA), applying method of regression (MR) at least for one of the biases, and applying these methods using all available inter-mission crossovers, i.e. without taking into account ascending/descending bias.

The mean inter-satellite elevation biases are positive (Table 1) indicating that elevations measured from ERS-2 and Envisat satellites are in average higher than those measured by ERS-1 and ERS-2 altimeters respectively. At the same time all elevation biases vary over Greenland ice sheet from -1.8 to 3.4 m with standard deviation of 0.5 to 0.6 m. Corresponding σ^0 biases (Table 2) are negative everywhere ranging from -9.8 to -1 dB, and in contrast to spatial distribution their averaged values do not show dependence on ascending/descending bias. ERS-2 ascending/descending biases are also highly variable (Fig. 2e and j) and ranges from 1.5 to 2.5 m for elevation and from -2.4 to 3.6 dB for σ^0 .

Because of rougher sloping surface and limited quantity and quality of the data especially over ice sheet margins only some of the biases could be found for some individual cell. Therefore in addition to biases averaged over different areas where they are available, Tables 1 and 2 present more comparable biases averaged over the same areas, where all biases were calculated. All biases were estimated over area of $1194.9 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ (768 cells) and $1284.9 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ (816 cells) for elevation and σ^0 respectively. All biases for both elevation and σ^0 were calculated for 757 cells over the area of $1177.4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ (Fig.2k). For some cells, if possible, one combined assessment of the biases was obtained using all available inter-satellite crossover points, i.e. without calculating two estimations of the biases and taking into account ascending/descending bias. If two estimations are available for other biases, then their mean was applied when forming time series over these cells. Applying these values to inter-satellite crossovers allowed creating merged time series over 81 cells covering $147.3 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ or 11% of the area, where elevation and σ^0 time series were formed (Fig. 2k). Thus, time series obtained by merging altimeter measurements from ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat satellites were formed using inter-satellite biases over 838 cells or area of $1324.6 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$.

Another reason limiting estimation of ERS-1/ERS-2 biases over the North-West coast close to the Nares strait is a non-optimized ERS-2 altimeter acquisition plan during the first 4 years of satellite operation. Although both – ERS-1 and ERS-2 – altimeters were operated in two – ice and ocean – modes, ice/ocean mode transitions occurred between 35-day cycles for ERS-1 altimeter, and near coastline for ERS-2. However only from March 1999 ERS-2 mode transitions was applied more closely to the ice or land boundaries and follow the coastline more precisely. Therefore lack of crossovers between ERS-1 and ERS-2 ice-mode measurements with dt close to 0 resulted in inability to determine ERS-1/ERS-2 biases over noted area.

2.2 Backscattered power discontinuity between ERS-1 measurements

In order to create time series of backscattered power the inconsistency between measurements from ERS-1 satellite before and after August 1993 should be taken into account.

Example at the Fig 1 demonstrates that while discontinuity of σ^0 is clearly pronounced, difference between AGC measurements is small and existence of its inconsistency is not apparent. Because of this discrepancy and strong linear relationship between AGC and σ^0 , difference between these two parameters ($AGC - \sigma^0$) give a robust criterion for sorting backscattered power measurements. This criterion allows separating backscattered power measurements independently from their temporal variations and also to reveal existing discontinuities. For ERS-1 ice-mode measurements $AGC - \sigma^0$ difference has two parts with remarkably different values of about 28 dB before 28th of July 1993 and 16 dB for the measurements after this date. It implies lack of crossovers differences between measurements related to these two different parts with small dt , and therefore ERS-1 backscattered power offset can not be found using the same method that was used for estimation of inter-satellite biases. It is aggravated by operating of the altimeter in ocean-mode during 35-day cycle started in 30 July 1993, i.e. two days after abrupt change in backscattered power.

Figure 3. Discontinuous change of the ERS-1 backscattered power 28th July 1993 for σ^0 (a) – (b) and AGC (c) – (d). (a) and (c) – $B_{ers1 d - ers1 a}$, (b) and (d) – $B_{ers1 a - ers1 d}$.

Therefore to estimate the discontinuous change of the ERS-1 backscattered power over individual grid cells we used backscattered power differences between measurements before and after 28th July 1993 located not far then 500 m from each other in addition to differences in crossover points, and applied MR in the same way as was used for calculation of inter-satellite biases. This approach can be applied since σ^0 and AGC are stable within one cells comparing with surface elevation, which is characterized by strong variability due to sloping and irregular surface. The discontinuous changes were calculated using regression of $d\sigma^0$ and $dAGC$ to dt as an offset of polynomial fit from the origin at the point with the least available dt . Due to absence of backscattered power differences with dt close to 0, the point with the least dt was used as the best approximation of abrupt changes. Since these assessments may be affected by changes of ice sheet surface elevation and properties, we took into account possible ascending/descending bias in the same way as for inter-satellite bias and calculated two estimates: $B_{ers1 d - ers1 a}$ and $B_{ers1 a - ers1 d}$ (Fig.

3). Both of them are in average of 13.4 ± 0.1 dB and 1.2 ± 0.1 dB for σ^0 and AGC respectively, but show noticeable difference in southern and western Greenland up to several dB indicating effect of ascending/descending bias. These estimates were calculated over about $1.6 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 10^3$ km² area, which cover the area where inter-satellite biases are available (Fig.2k).

σ^0 and AGC discontinuous changes have similar features of distribution and we suggest that differences of AGC values between two periods indicate only change of ice sheet surface properties, while those differences of σ^0 resulted also from changes of the method for their calculation. It is clearly seen from ERS-1 AGC and σ^0 3-months averaged time series formed by technique described in the next section for one of the cell in North-East Greenland, where the largest ERS-1 backscattered power bias discontinuous changes were found (Fig. 4). Time series without applying obtained discontinuous change for AGC shows that two parts before and after summer 1993 are generally consistent with each other, while uncorrected σ^0 time series indicates their significant discrepancy. Local minimum of backscattered power in summer 1993 resulted in a high value of calculated discontinuous changes and their applying to the first part of σ^0 and AGC time series gives unreasonably high values. Therefore to create time series of σ^0 we applied for each cell difference between two calculated abrupt changes ($B_{\sigma^0} - B_{AGC}$) to σ^0 crossover differences between measurements before and after July 28th 1993. This allows taking into account changes in ice sheet surface properties in addition to changes in method of determination of σ^0 values. Over most of cells ($B_{\sigma^0} - B_{AGC}$) difference ranges between 12.1 and 12.3 dB with the average of 12.2 dB for both $B_{ers1 d - ers1 a}$ and $B_{ers1 a - ers1 d}$.

Figure 4. ERS-1 σ^0 and AGC time series for the area 78.5-79°N and 25-26°W. All time series are referenced to the autumn 1993: uncorrected AGC (black), uncorrected σ^0 (red), σ^0 corrected by applying of estimated discontinuous change (violet), and σ^0 corrected by applying of differences between discontinuous changes of AGC and σ^0 (blue) before autumn 1993. All σ^0 time series after autumn 1993 (green) are coincide with each other and in close agreement with AGC.

In order to check weather using differences between all measurement located within 500 m in addition to crossovers is justified we estimated ERS-1 backscattered power discontinuous change applying the same method, but using only crossovers available within individual cell. For the cells, where the least dt , which were used for calculation of these two estimations of the discontinuous

change, differ by less than 90 days, high correlation coefficients of about 0.9 between the results were found. Thus this good agreement indicated small influence of including differences between measurements located 500 m away from each other.

3. Creating of time series

Through applying inter-satellite biases to corresponding ERS-1×ERS-2, ERS-2×Envisat and ERS-1×Envisat crossover differences, and ERS-1 backscattered power discontinuous change to ERS-1×ERS-1 crossovers 3-month averaged time series of elevation and σ^0 from April 1992 to December 2008 were created for individual cells. The approach used for time series generation is based on technique described in details in [Li and Davis, 2006], which we developed in order to include more measurements for elevation change calculations. After generation of one-sided $N \times N$ matrix of averaged elevation-change values $\{dH_{i \times j}, i = 1, \dots, N, j \geq i\}$ between all possible time intervals in [Li and Davis, 2006] all rows in the matrix were referenced to the selected referenced row $i = R$ to ensure that they are referenced to the same time period. The row with maximum number of nonzero matrix elements $\{dH_{R \times j} \neq 0\}$ was selected as referenced to increase number of nonzero elements throughout the matrix. Time series in each row were referenced to the same row using:

$$dH_{i \times j} = \begin{cases} dH_{i \times j} + dH_{R \times i}, i > R \\ dH_{i \times j} - dH_{i \times R}, i < R \end{cases}$$

Then averaged elevation change for each time interval was computed using available nonzero matrix elements of corresponding matrix column. However using one-sided matrix may limit number of nonzero matrix elements used for determination of averaged elevation change for any matrix column j , i.e. for any time interval. Although upper and lower triangular matrix of elevation-change values are symmetric with opposite sign ($dH_{i \times j} = -dH_{j \times i}$), each element with $i < j$ after referencing to selected row R also can be used for computation of averaged elevation change of the corresponding time interval. Both nonzero matrix elements $-dH_{i \times j}$ and $dH_{j \times i}$ can be used when averaging different matrix columns j and i making their contribution to the mean values. Moreover, as a corollary of it, if matrix elements $dH_{i \times R}$ are zero elements for all $i < R$, then all averaged elevation-change values with $j < R$ cannot be determined when using only one-sided matrix. At the same time any nonzero matrix element $dH_{i \times j}$ with $i > R$ and $j < R$ may be used for calculation of averaged elevation change for corresponding time interval j . Therefore two-sided matrix was used in order to take more non-matrix elements into account when calculating elevation change for any time interval.

Furthermore different rows of matrix may contain different set of nonzero elements and row with maximum number of nonzero matrix elements may not contain some elements available for other rows. Therefore to increase number of used nonzero matrix elements the matrix was referenced to all rows, which have at least one nonzero element with $i \neq j$, producing N matrixes referenced to different rows. If considering two-sided matrix all obtained matrixes give the same set of points j in their averaged time series. Therefore elevation-change time series can be formed as a mean of time series derived from all of these matrixes. The same technique was applied to form σ^0 time series using measurements related to corresponding elevation measurements. This technique was applied to create elevation and σ^0 time series over 16.5-year time period 1992-2008 for each individual grid cells 1° latitude \times 0.5° .

Because of lack of the measurements in the southern Greenland and over ice sheet margins only 3-month averaged time series can be formed for most of individual grid cells in these areas. In order to obtain time series with one-month resolution we applied technique described above for creating 3-month averaged time series, but with one-month step. Each point of these time series is 3-month time interval, but time intervals of adjacent points are overlapping and differing by one month, for example: January to March, February to April, March to May, etc. The obtained time series represents combination of three time series formed using 3-month nonoverlapping time intervals, but with different months included in these intervals. Thus the resulting time series consist of 199 points starting from interval April to June 1992 and ending with the interval October to December 2008.

However time series for different cells may contain different set of time intervals and, as a result of applied technique, can be referenced to different rows. Therefore when forming time series over certain area (e.g. drainage basin or elevation band) time series of individual cells cannot be averaged. Therefore differences between points of time series, which are not depending on reference row, were used [Li and Davis, 2006]. But using only one common reference time interval as performed in [Li and Davis, 2006] again may limit the data used for calculating averaged time series because time series for individual cells may have different gaps. Therefore for every cell the matrix of differences between points of time series was generated $\{\Delta dH_{ij} = dH_j - dH_i, i = 1, \dots, N, j = 1, \dots, N\}$. Averaging of corresponding available ΔdH_{ij} values for all cells over studied area gives the averaged matrix. Then average differences in every column representing time interval j gives the average time series of the differences between points ΔdH_j for the area. The time series were obtained from:

$$dH_j = 0, \text{ if } j = 1$$

$$dH_j = dH_{j-1} + \Delta dH_j, \text{ if } j > 1.$$

4. Effect of the biases on estimation of elevation change

Applying our new method used for assessment of biases to ERS-1 and ERS-2 measurements results in lowering by 1.3 cm/year our previous estimation of elevation change from 1992 to 2003 of 5.3 cm/year obtained using time series method [Johannessen et al., 2005]. Moreover because of excluding the areas with negative elevation change rates over cost in the North-East Greenland from the new estimation the difference between the results would be even larger.

Elevation change from merged time series from April 1992 to December 2008 without applying determined biases shows overestimation of elevation change over the same area in average by 6.6 cm/year and ranges from -1.0 to 25.9 cm/year with standard deviation of 4.4 cm/year. Largest values are observed close to the margins, while over large portion of central areas the difference of elevation change rates varies within 1-2 cm/year. As noted in [Zwally et al., 2005], although biases are correlated with received backscatter power, surface slope and surface elevation, “it was not possible to formulate the bias as a consistent function of these parameters over all of the ice sheet”.

For creating elevation time series from ERS-1 and ERS-2 altimeter measurements over Antarctic ice sheet Davis et al. [2005] did not use inter-satellite crossovers and adjusted together time series obtained separately from different satellites. This approach avoids necessity to apply inter-satellite biases, but ignore large amount of inter-satellite crossovers as discussed above. Besides possibility of application of such approach for Greenland ice sheet should be assessed. Compared with Antarctic ice sheet large part of southern Greenland located in lower latitudes, where altimeter measurements are sparser, and where surface is more undulating especially over margin areas. Nevertheless we compared elevation change estimations obtained from merged time series using two independent approaches, i.e. by applying inter-satellite biases and by adjusting separate time series for different satellites in order to confirm the validity of merging the measurements.

First, we created 3-months averaged with 1-month step elevation time series separately from ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat satellite measurements applying the same technique as we used to obtain merged time series. In order to adjust them together we used points, where time series are overlapping, i.e. 11 points (MJJ 1995 to MAM 1996) to adjust ERS-1 and ERS-2 time series, and 7 points (OND 2002 to AMJ 2003) to adjust ERS-2 and Envisat time series.

To adjust ERS-1 and 2 time series we formed two matrixes using differences between 11 overlapping points of elevation time series for each satellite:

$$(\Delta dH_{ers-1})_{ij} = (dH_{ers-1})_j - (dH_{ers-1})_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, 11, j = 1, \dots, 11$$

$$(\Delta dH_{ers-2})_{ij} = (dH_{ers-2})_j - (dH_{ers-2})_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, 11, j = 1, \dots, 11$$

Then we found means between corresponding values of the matrixes

$$(\Delta dH_{m_ers-1/ers-2})_{ij} = ((\Delta dH_{ers-1})_{ij} + (\Delta dH_{ers-2})_{ij}) / 2,$$

if they are available for both matrixes and their difference is less then resulting standard error (SE)

of the $(\Delta dH_{m_ers-1/ers-2})_{ij}$, i.e. $(SE_{m_ers1/ers2})_{ij} = \sqrt{(SE_{ers-1})_{ij}^2 + (SE_{ers-2})_{ij}^2}$, where $(SE_{ers-1})_{ij}$ and

$(SE_{ers-2})_{ij}$ are SE of $(\Delta dH_{ers-1})_{ij}$ and $(\Delta dH_{ers-2})_{ij}$, which were calculated using similar equation for

SE of $(dH_{ers-1})_i$, $(dH_{ers-1})_j$, $(dH_{ers-2})_i$ and $(dH_{ers-2})_j$. Then adjusted time series for the points

common for ERS-1 and ERS-2 time series were obtained as

$$(\Delta dH_{ers-1/ers-2})_j = \sum_{i=1}^N (\Delta dH_{m_ers-1/ers-2})_{ij} / N,$$

where N – number of nonzero matrix elements in the column j . Values $(\Delta dH_{ers-1/ers-2})_j$ were

obtained only for those columns j , where nonzero matrix elements with $i \neq j$ are available. Since all

such columns have the same set of matrix elements $(\Delta dH_{m_ers-1/ers-2})_{ij}$, i.e. they are available in the

same rows, then all points of adjusted time series $(\Delta dH_{ers-1/ers-2})_j$ are referenced to the same time

interval. ERS-2 and Envisat time series were adjusted applying the same approach using 7 common

points of their time series.

Figure 5. (a) Differences between elevation change rates obtained using these two approaches: by applying inter-satellite biases and by adjusting separate time series for different satellites. Average absolute differences between nonzero matrix elements used for adjusting time series obtained separately for (b) ERS-1 and ERS-2 satellites, and (c) ERS-2 and Envisat satellites.

Then the points of ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat elevation time series before MJJ 1995, from AMJ 1996 to SON 2002 and after AMJ 2003 respectively were adjusted accordingly to form time series from 1992 to 2008. Merged time series were formed for the cells where number of available points common for ERS-1 and ERS-2, and ERS-2 and Envisat measurements is more then 5 and 3 respectively. It results in adjustment of separate time series from different satellites over 807 cells

covering $1261.8 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ or 95% of the area covered by the results obtained when applying biases. Differences between elevation change rates obtained using these two approaches show good agreement for central northern regions within $\pm 1 \text{ cm/year}$ and increases toward southern and costal areas (Fig. 5a). This distribution corresponds, from the one side, to distributions of time interval dt , which appeared sufficient for obtaining assessment of the biases, and, from the other side, to distribution of average absolute differences between nonzero matrix elements used for adjusting time series obtained separately for different satellites. These average differences were determined as (if adjusting ERS-1 and ERS-2 time series) $\sum |(\Delta dH_{ers-1})_{ij} - (\Delta dH_{ers-2})_{ij}| / 2$, $i = 1, \dots, 11, j = 1, \dots, 11$ and represent disagreement between time series related to different satellites (Fig. 5b-c). The average difference of $0.09 \pm 0.07 \text{ cm/year}$ between the results over regions, where results from both approach are available, was found indicating small influence of approach used for merging the time series on estimation of average elevation change rate. At the same time estimating and applying inter-satellite biases allow using significantly larger number of crossover points and therefore assess elevation change over larger area and with better accuracy.

5. Correction for correlation between elevation and backscattered power changes

Correction using constant correlation gradient

One of the important corrections of elevation change time series, its seasonal and interannual variations is adjustment for correlation between changes of elevation and σ^0 [Wingham et al., 1998, Davis and Ferguson, 2004] or AGC [Zwally et al., 2005] as a measure of received backscattered power. This correction was determined over individual grid cells for each point i of time series as product of backscattered power change in the point i and the gradient representing the magnitude in elevation change for change in backscattered power. Then corrected elevation change dH_{i_cor} for point i was found by subtraction of the correction as (when using σ^0)

$$dH_{i_cor} = dH_i - (dH / d\sigma^0) \cdot d\sigma_i^0$$

High correlation coefficients between elevation and σ^0 time series for the Antarctic ice sheet – were found in two studies: larger then 0.7 for most locations in [Wingham et al., 1998] and 0.64 in average over all studied areas in [Davis and Ferguson, 2004] with correlation exceeding 0.7 only for half of the cells. [Davis and Ferguson, 2004] supposed that the main factor resulting in this distinction is differences between satellite altimeter instruments (ERS-1 measurements were used in [Wingham et al., 1998] and ERS-2 in [Davis and Ferguson, 2004]), and between retracking algorithms. At the same time we believe that length of the time period used for correlation and gradient determination is one of the important causes for observed difference. Whereas 5-year

period 1995-2000 of ERS-2 satellite observation was used in [Davis and Ferguson, 2004], Wingham et al. [1998] used only 18 month of ERS-1 data (June 1993–December 1994) for estimating $dH/d\sigma^0$ gradient. Due to discrepancy in temporal variations of elevation and σ^0 correlation may become weaker with increasing of length of considered time period. For example, if time series of elevation and σ^0 are dispersed after some point, then correlation becomes much lower, even if temporal variations are in agreement before and after this point. It resulted in higher correlation coefficient obtained in [Wingham et al., 1998], where shorter time period was using for estimating correlation and gradient. At the same time low correlation generally corresponds to a low gradient $dH/d\sigma^0$ and, therefore, to underestimation of correction.

Figure 6. Comparison of conventional and improved techniques of adjustment for correlation between elevation and σ^0 changes. Correlation between elevation and σ^0 time series (a)-(b), correction gradient $dH/d\sigma^0$ (c) and $\Delta dH/\Delta d\sigma^0$ (d), σ^0 change rate (e), correction obtained by two techniques (f)-(g) and their difference (h).

This problem is more important for Greenland ice sheet, where temporal variability of elevation and backscattered power is higher than over Antarctic due to large variability in

accumulation and summer melting over low-elevation areas. Average correlation coefficient between time series of elevation and σ^0 , which we used as more accurate estimate of backscattered power, was 0.26. Correlation exceeds 0.7 only for some cells in the high elevation areas, while over most of studied area of Greenland it is lower than 0.3 (Fig. 6a).

To overcome the problem associated with high temporal variability differences between adjacent points of time series were used to create the new time series:

$$\Delta dH_i = dH_i - dH_{i-1}, \quad \Delta d\sigma_i^0 = d\sigma_i^0 - d\sigma_{i-1}^0, \quad i = 2, \dots, N,$$

where N – number of time interval, for which dH_i and $d\sigma_i^0$ are available. ΔdH_i and $\Delta d\sigma_i^0$ points contain only changes between two adjacent points of initial time series representing changes during j time interval. Then disagreements between any corresponding points of dH_i and $d\sigma_i^0$ time series do not affect general agreement of the whole time series. Better overall agreement between new time series results in higher average correlation coefficient of 0.39 and correlation higher than 0.5 over almost half of the studied area (Fig. 6b). Average correlation gradient $\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0$ of 11.1 cm/dB obtained from new time series is by 1.1 cm/dB higher than gradient obtained for original time series (Fig. 6c-d) resulting in higher absolute value of correction for elevation change. Correlation coefficients (Fig. 6a-b) and correlation gradients (Fig. 6c-d) correspond to each other indicating in general higher and lower values over central and margin areas respectively. Effect of correction on estimation of elevation change rate dH / dt , i.e. differences between trends in elevation before and after adjustment are shown in Figures 6f-g. In average corrections were 0.35 cm/year and 0.23 cm/year when using $dH / d\sigma^0$ and $\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0$ gradients respectively. The corrections are small in average because of low average $d\sigma^0$ change rates (Fig.7), which is amounted to 0.01 dB/year, but can be large locally and ranges between ± 30 dB/year (Fig. 6e). Small lowering of average correction when using $\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0$ gradient by 0.12 cm/year (Fig. 6h) is caused by two reasons. First is a negative rate of $d\sigma^0$ change in vast north-eastern areas of Greenland and over its central region around 71° N, where $\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0$ values are remarkably higher than $dH / d\sigma^0$ ones. Second reason is slightly lower $\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0$ gradient in the areas, where it is generally high. Although average corrections and their difference are small, their local values can be up to several cm/year. Correction found using $\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0$ gradient ranges from -3.6 to 3.5 cm/year with standard deviation 0.81 cm/year. Difference between corrections (Fig.6h) ranges from -6.0 to 5.6 cm/year with standard deviation 0.76 cm/year.

Figure 7. Averaged over Greenland ice sheet time series of backscatter coefficient $d\sigma^0$ (thick line) and their differences between adjacent points $\Delta d\sigma^0$ (thin line).

Correction using variable correlation gradient

The described method of adjusting elevation time series for its dependency on backscatter power imply using constant correlation gradient obtained either from the original time series, $dH/d\sigma^0$, or from new time series of differences between adjacent points $\Delta dH/\Delta d\sigma^0$. However value of the gradient may vary not only spatially but also temporally because of changes of ice sheet surface properties in time. Although Davis and Ferguson [2004] noted that they did not find significant temporal variability of $dH/d\sigma^0$ over five-year time series over Antarctic ice sheet, this can be not the case when using 16,5-year time-series over Greenland ice sheet. To estimate temporal changes of the gradient we calculated it for every point of time series using several preceding and several following points: $\Delta dH_{i-k}, \dots, \Delta dH_{i+k}$ and $\Delta d\sigma^0_{i-k}, \dots, \Delta d\sigma^0_{i+k}$, where k – number of ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$ points before and after point i .

Since the gradient may be depending on both – inter-annual and seasonal – variations, two estimations of the gradient were calculated and then combined into one. One estimation, $(\Delta dH/\Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$, was performed using consecutive points surrounding the point for which the gradient is calculating. In this case we used $k=8$, i.e. gradients were calculated using 18 points (1.5 years) of time series formed as 3-month averaged with one month step. Second estimation, $(\Delta dH/\Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$, was obtained from ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$ values related to the same 3-month interval (JFM or FMA or MAM, etc.) in the different years in order to assess possible seasonality of the gradient. For the second estimation we used $k=2$, i.e. 5 points (5 years) for every 3-month interval. Thus, using differences between adjacent points (ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$) allow not only reducing influence of discrepancy between elevation and σ^0 time series, but also estimating seasonal variations of the correlation gradient. Small amount of points used for estimation of

$(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ values is especially critical in the beginning and in the end of time series, i.e. for first and last two points, where less than 5 points can be used. Moreover it is aggravated by the data gaps resulted from the instrument operation during the first years of ERS-1 satellite measurements and from on-board Envisat altimeter anomaly during February to June 2006. Therefore to calculate gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ for the first and last 3 points we used 5 years in the beginning and in the end of time series respectively. If number of available points required for calculation of the gradient for any point was less than 3, then this gradient was equated to 0 to produce zero correction of elevation change for corresponding point of time series.

Figure 8. Averaged over Greenland ice sheet correlation gradients determined for each point of time series (a) from surrounding points $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ (blue) and from points related to the same 3-month interval for different years $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ (red), and (b) by combining these estimations using (1).

Discrepancy between averaged over Greenland time series of the gradient obtained using two methods described above is clearly shown in Figure 8a. Estimation of the gradient obtained from surrounding points of time series $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ represents relative changes of

ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$ during the current 1.5 years but ignore any seasonal variations. Gradient obtained by the second method, $\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}$, shows seasonal variations typically with higher values in winter and spring, and lower values in summer and autumn, but does not reveal rapid inter-annual fluctuations, for example, maximum observed from the $\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}$ estimations in 2000-2001. Nevertheless both $-\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}$ and $\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}$ – estimations indicate decadal changes with relatively high values till 2001 followed by their reducing with a minimum occurred in 2006.

In order to use advantages of both methods used for calculation of the gradient we found its combined estimation for every point i of time series $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{combined}\right)_i$ by correcting corresponding values $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}\right)_i$ for the average difference between gradients $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}\right)_j$ and $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}\right)_j$ related to the same 3-month interval (JFM or FMA or MAM, etc.) in the 5 years surrounding point i as

$$\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{combined}\right)_i = \left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}\right)_i - \frac{\sum_{j=i-k}^{i+k} \left(\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}\right)_j - \left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}\right)_j \right)}{n} \quad (1),$$

where $k = 2$ and n – number of available differences $\left(\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}\right)_j - \left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}\right)_j \right)$. For the first and last three points differences $\left(\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}\right)_j - \left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}\right)_j \right)$ were calculated using 5 years in the beginning and in the end of time series respectively. In the cases of large amount of data gaps resulting in $n = 0$ then $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}\right)_i$, if available, or $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}\right)_i$ were used as an estimation of the combined gradient. If $n = 0$ and both $-\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}\right)_i$ and $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}\right)_i$ – are not available, then $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{combined}\right)_i$ was equated to 0 to produce 0 correction. Time series of combined estimations of the gradient $\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{combined}$ (Fig. 8b) includes the features of variations of the gradients $\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{consecutive}$ and $\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{season}$ on different time scales taking into account both seasonal and inter-annual changes.

Time series of correlation coefficients between ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$ for corresponding correlation gradients also show seasonal and inter-annual variations (Fig. 9). Correlation coefficients related to combined estimation of the gradient were found by the same method as was used for calculation of the gradient $\left(\left(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0\right)_{combined}\right)_i$. Although this estimation of correlation is not obtained directly from comparison of two parameters, it can be useful for comparing with

corresponding values of the correlation gradient. Figures 8 and 9 show that time series of correlation coefficients only partly follow time series of corresponding gradients. At the same time spatial distributions of the correlation coefficient (Fig. 10a-c) and the gradient (Fig. 10d-f) determined as averaged values from the whole time series over individual cell are generally in agreement.

Figure 9. Averaged over Greenland ice sheet correlation coefficients corresponding (a) to $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ gradients (blue) and to $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ gradients (red), and (b) to combined estimation of the gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$.

In order to take into account temporal changes of correlation gradient we determined correction for elevation changes ΔdH resulted from correlation between values ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$ over individual cells for each point i of time series as $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_i \cdot \Delta d\sigma^0_i$, where $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_i$ are estimations of the gradient: $((\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive})_i$, $((\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season})_i$ and $((\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined})_i$.

Time series of accumulated correction indicating its overall effect on estimation of elevation change was found as

$$(dH_{cor})_i = 0, \quad \text{for } i=1$$

$$(dH_{cor})_i = dH_{i-1} + (\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_i \cdot \Delta d\sigma_i^0, \quad \text{for } i>1.$$

Although time series of corrections $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_i \cdot \Delta d\sigma_i^0$ averaged over Greenland ice sheet reveal their similarity (Fig.11a), accumulated corrections indicate significantly different effect on elevation change estimation (Fig.11b). One of the reasons of that is the inter-annual changes of the correlation gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$, $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$. Elevation corrections determined using these gradients are larger then that obtained using constant gradient before 2002 and lower for the period after 2002 following the time series of the gradients (Fig.8), which are reducing over most part of Greenland with approximately the same rate for different gradients (Fig. 10g-I, Table 3). The least effect of temporal changes of the gradients on accumulated corrections is resulted when using gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$, which is more smoothed as based on 5-year time intervals. As a result corrections obtained using gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ have an overall effect on elevation change by 2.4-2.5 cm/year larger then those obtained when using constant gradient or gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ (Table 3). Since the corrections are to be subtracted from elevation change then applying corrections obtained using gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ significantly decreases the overall estimation of elevation change for considered period over Greenland ice sheet.

Another reason of the differences between corrections is seasonal changes of the applied gradients. Average contribution of the different 3-month intervals to variations in backscatter coefficient $\Delta d\sigma^0$, correlation gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$, corresponding correlation coefficients and resulting correction of elevation change over different elevation zones are shown in the Figure 12. Backscatter coefficient $\Delta d\sigma^0$ has a strong maximum in end of summer - beginning of autumn and secondary in winter. When using constant gradient only these changes of backscatter power affect seasonal variations of correction of elevation change. Correlation gradient has completely different seasonal behavior with minimum in the beginning of summer and maximum in the end of the spring. Moreover while seasonal variations of averaged values $\Delta d\sigma^0$ are similar over different zones, gradient is significantly lower over low-elevation areas, where it varies around 0 with larger amplitude following spatial distribution of correlation coefficients. In fact backscatter coefficient over low-elevation area characterized by higher variability then over central parts of Greenland especially in summer months, and only averaged values indicate similar behavior over different zones.

Figure 10. Distribution of (a)-(c) averaged within each cell correlation coefficient between ΔdH_i and $\Delta d\sigma_i^0$ values, (d)-(f) their averaged within each cell correlation gradient, (g)-(i) gradient change rate, and (j)-(l) correction of elevation change rate determined using different correlation gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$, $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$.

Figure 11. Time series of (a) correction and (b) accumulated correction of elevation change determined using different correlation gradients: constant over individual cell (green), $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ (blue), $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ (red) and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ (black).

	Method of gradient determination			
	Constant	Consecutive	Season	Combined
Correlation	0.39±0.01	0.47±0.01	0.41±0.01	0.40±0.01
Gradient, cm/dB	11.1±0.4	15.3±0.3	14.0±0.3	14.0±0.3
Gradient change, cm/dB/year	–	-0.88±0.04	-0.92±0.05	-0.83±0.04
Correction, cm/year	0.23±0.03	2.62±0.20	0.14±0.60	2.61±0.61

Table 3. Spatially averaged correlation coefficient, correlation gradient, gradient change rate and correction of elevation change rate for different correlation gradients: $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$, $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$.

Figure 12. Seasonal variations of the backscatter coefficient $\Delta d\sigma^0$, correlation gradient $(\Delta dH/\Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$, corresponding correlation coefficient between ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$, and correction for elevation change ΔdH . (a) over whole Greenland ($\Delta d\sigma^0$ - blue, $(\Delta dH/\Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ - red, correlation - green, correction for ΔdH - black), and (b)-(e) over whole Greenland (black) and different elevation zones: >2000m (blue), >1500m (sky blue), <2000m (orange) and <1500 (red).

Nevertheless correction of elevation change determined as $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_i \cdot \Delta d\sigma_i^0$ for each point of time series over individual cell is the result of superimposed gradient and backscatter coefficient. In comparison with the case of using constant gradient absolute correction becomes higher in winter and spring (when it is typically negative), and lower in summer and autumn (when it is positive in summer and early autumn, and negative in late autumn). Correction over high-elevation area closely follows variations of $\Delta d\sigma^0$ indicating that σ^0 is the dominating factor for seasonal changes of correction here. Over ice sheet margins contribution of the gradient becomes prevailed for estimation of correction, which has almost opposite seasonal distribution.

Figure 13. Average differences between accumulated corrections and differences between corrections for individual points ΔdH obtained using $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ gradients. Specific points, which most contribute to the differences are marked with a circles.

As one more reason of the difference between corrections when using different correlation gradients we may note influence of specific points of the time series. If consider corrections obtained from temporary variable gradients, the most discrepancy is observed between correction resulted from gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ and two other gradients. Figure 13 shows average differences between accumulated corrections and differences between corrections for individual points ΔdH obtained using gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$. Although the differences of values ΔdH are mostly positive resulting in rising of accumulated correction before 2002 it is seen that points related to the summers 1995 (MJJ), 2000 (JJA, JAS, ASO) and 2002 (MJJ) contribute most to the difference. Such points are resulted from the differences in the methods of determination of gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$. Smoothed gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ represents 5-year period taking into account primarily seasonal changes, while $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ gradient implicates advantages of both gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ representing better inter-annual changes as well as taking into account

seasonal variations. In summers 1995 and 2002 $\Delta d\sigma^0$ values are mostly negative over southern and northern Greenland respectively. At the same time gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ are typically lower than $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ ones in these areas resulting in less negative corrections over part of the Greenland and consequently higher positive correction over whole Greenland. In summer 2000 $\Delta d\sigma^0$ values are mostly positive, while gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ are higher over whole Greenland, therefore the correction is also higher when using combined gradient.

Spatial distribution of the effect of correction on elevation change rate estimation is also different when using different correlation gradients (Figs. 6g and 10j-l). Corrections of elevation change rate obtained from temporary variable gradients and their spatial variability (Table 3) are order of magnitude more than for the case of using constant gradient. Correction corresponding to the gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ has remarkably larger spatial variability than that obtained from gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$, and correction derived from applying combined gradient shows combination of features of these two distributions. However none of distributions of correction obtained from temporary variable gradients has remarkable similarity with corrections obtained from constant gradient.

6. Estimation of elevation change and discussion

After time series of Greenland ice sheet surface elevation from 1992 to 2008 were formed they were adjusted for correlation between elevation and σ^0 . Different estimations of elevation change rates were obtained by applying different corrections for correlation estimated using constant and variable correlation gradients (Figure 14-16, Table 4). As noted above applying gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ allow better to reveal inter-annual variations of correction, while gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ takes into account its seasonal changes. Indicated seasonal variations of the gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ (Fig. 8 and Fig. 12) confirm that the volume scattering on the observed altimeter returns from the ice sheet surface due to penetration of part of the radar signal through the surface is the main reason of correlation between elevation and backscattered power [Legresy and Remy 1998]. Increased snow densification and larger the size of the snow grains in the firn induced by higher summer temperature result in smaller penetration of the signal during summer and autumn, while during cold winter and spring larger signal penetration results in higher $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ values. Then abrupt decreasing of the gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ started in 2001 (Fig. 8) may represent effect of lifting of the radar-reflection horizon proposed in [Thomas et al., 2008] as a response to increased surface melting of the Greenland ice sheet in 2000s. Although

effect of increased melting during last decade on elevation change is mostly indicated over low-elevation margin areas (Figure 16), surface properties in the vast ice sheet interior areas may also be changed due to observed increased melt extent [Steffen et al., 2004; Tedesco 2007]. Thus, time series of correlation gradient likely reveal changes of the snowpack characteristics, which are not reflected in backscattered power change (Fig. 7).

Region	Area, $\times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$	Method of gradient determination				
		Without correction	Constant	Consecutive	Season	Combined
Whole Greenland	1324.6	3.4±0.2	3.2±0.2	0.8±0.3	3.3±0.7	0.8±0.6
> 1500 m	1179.6	4.7±0.2	4.4±0.2	1.8±0.2	4.2±0.5	1.3±0.5
< 1500 m	145.0	-6.9±0.9	-6.8±0.9	-7.1±1.1	-4.2±3.8	-6.0±3.6
West	557.8	4.9±0.4	4.5±0.4	2.8±0.5	4.3±1.4	1.8±1.3
North-East	631.5	2.4±0.3	2.4±0.2	-0.5±0.3	1.4±0.6	-2.3±0.7
South-East	135.4	2.0±0.7	1.3±0.7	-1.5±1.0	8.1±2.5	5.6±2.7

Table 4. Spatially averaged elevation change rate over different areas determined without taking into account correlation between elevation and σ^0 , and by applying corrections calculated using different correlation gradients: constant over individual cell, $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$, $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$.

Figure 14. Time series of elevation change determined without taking into account correlation between elevation and σ^0 (purple) and by applying corrections calculated using different correlation gradients: constant over individual cell (green), $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ (blue), $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ (red) and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$ (black).

Figure 15. Elevation change rates derived by merging ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat satellite altimeter measurements from 1992 to 2008 when applying (a) constant gradient and (b) gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$, (c) gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ and (d) gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$.

Although average time series of the gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ helps to interpret observed changes of the correlation gradients, correction for correlation and corrected elevation change rate determined using gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ are very noisy showing significant spatial variability (Fig. 10k and 15c). It is resulted from the method of calculation of the gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$, which uses small number of points (5 points) of time series distributed over long time period (5 years). Despite observed seasonal variations of the gradient it may significantly differ from year to year over 5-year period. And even if one of the ratios $\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0$ significantly differ from other 4, which are used for calculation the gradient for the point i $((\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season})_i$, it may essentially influence estimation of the gradient. At the same time it was shown that for the most of the Greenland ice sheet in the high-elevation areas seasonal changes of correction for correlation between ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$ is dominated by variations of $\Delta d\sigma^0$ (Fig. 12). Over low-elevation areas seasonal changes of the gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ become important, but small amount of available altimeter measurements here and, consequently, presence of the gaps in the time series aggravate problem associated with small number of points of time series. High variability of correction and corrected elevation change rates is also observed when using gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{combined}$, which implicates features of the gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{season}$ (Fig. 10l and 15d). Therefore we believe that more reasonable estimation of elevation change over Greenland can be obtained from adjustment of elevation time series by applying corrections calculated using gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$.

Figure 16 shows difference in elevation time series over high and low-elevation areas obtained using constant and $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ gradients. Lowering of elevation change rates estimations when applying temporally variable correlation gradient (Table 4) are resulted from divergence of the time series before 2001, which is originated from the difference between the gradients discussed in the previous section. Considering short time intervals for calculation variable gradients results in better agreement between ΔdH and $\Delta d\sigma^0$ time series, higher average correlation coefficient and, therefore, higher average variable gradients than average constant gradient (Table 3). Gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ is by about 9 cm/dB larger than the average constant gradient before 2001, and only by about 2 cm/dB smaller after 2001 (Fig. 8). Since all gradients – variable and constant – are close to 0 over margins (Fig. 6d, 10d-f) difference between elevation change rates is only 0.3 cm/year for low-elevation areas below 1500 m and more pronounced (2.4 cm/year) over interior areas (Table 4). Spatial distributions also indicate that

Figure 16. Elevation time series over the areas (a) above 1500 m and (b) below 1500 m obtained by applying (blue) constant gradient and (red) gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$

applying gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ gives essentially lower elevation change rates over most of the Greenland ice sheet areas (Fig. 15b). The presented results represent elevation changes over about 76% of the whole Greenland ice sheet, 87% of the area above 1500m and only 38% of the margins areas below 1500m, where amount of available crossovers are limited due to rougher sloping surface. Therefore involving more costal areas would result in faster thinning than found -7.1 cm/year for the whole considered period and -12.1 cm/year from OND 1999 to OND 2008.

Nevertheless, main features of spatial distribution with elevation growing over high-elevation areas and shrinking over ice sheet margins remains for both estimations. Increases in surface elevation, which were observed over central regions of Greenland from 1995 have decelerated over the period from 2003 to 2005 and changed to elevation decrease during 2006-2008. In contrast, surface-elevation decreases from 2000 in the low-elevation areas of ice sheet have continued due to enhanced summer melting and especially pronounced in 2008.

Elevation zone	Laser altimetry dH/dt, cm/year	Radar altimetry				Difference (radar – laser)	
		dH/dt, cm/year (const. grad.)	dH/dt, cm/year (var. grad.)	Area,* 10 ³ km ²	%	dH/dt, cm/year (const. grad.)	dH/dt, cm/year (var. grad.)
Overall	-4.5	4.9±0.3	1.6±0.4	1324.6	76	9.4	6.1
> 1500 m	1.2	6.0±0.3	2.4±0.4	1179.6	87	4.8	1.2
> 2000 m	2.4	6.3±0.3	2.9±0.4	955.4	92	3.9	0.5
< 1500 m	-25.7	-4.8±1.2	-5.2±2.1	145.0	38	20.9	20.5
< 2000 m	-15.3	1.2±0.8	-1.9±1.1	369.3	53	16.5	13.4

Table 5. Comparison of elevation change rates derived from laser altimeter surveys and from satellite radar altimeter measurements when applying constant and variable gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$. Area and % indicate the area and percentage of specific region, where the estimates derived from radar altimeter measurements are available.

We compared elevation change estimates obtained by applying constant and temporally varying gradients $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ with those derived from merged analysis of surveys with airborne laser altimeter and from ICESat laser altimeter measurements. Although laser altimeter measurements are sparse in time and space comparing with radar altimetry, they do not affected by the errors associated with signal penetration in snow. The longest time periods for which the elevation changes from laser altimetry are reported are the periods from May-June 1993 to May-June 2004 and from June-July 1994 to June-July 2004 for South and North of Greenland respectively [Thomas 2006]. Therefore we estimated elevation change rates from radar altimeter measurements between AMJ points of time series: from 1993 to 2004 and from 1994 to 2004 over areas to the south and to the north of 72°N respectively. Then we averaged these two estimates weighting them by the corresponding areas and compared with elevation change rates obtained from laser altimetry. Table 5 shows that the results obtained from laser and radar altimetry, if applying variable gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$, are in good agreement over high-elevation areas where the coverage by laser and radar altimeter measurements are close. 92% of the ice sheet areas above 2000 m are involved in calculation of the elevation change from satellite radar altimetry where small difference of 0.5 cm/year was found. Relatively small difference is also observed over areas above 1500 m. Whereas for the low-elevation regions below 2000 m, where thinning rates are highest, only 53% of the ice sheet are involved resulting in large discrepancy between the average values. Thus we believe that adjusting elevation time series for correlation with backscattered

power by applying variable gradients properly takes into account changes of the ice sheet surface scattering characteristics and is able to provide with the reliable elevation change estimates.

Figure 17. Elevation time series obtained by applying gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ over different zones of Greenland (a) western (basins 1 to 5), (b) north-eastern (basins 6 to 9), and (c) south-eastern (basins 10 to 12).

	Whole time period	AMJ 1992 – AMJ 1995	AMJ 1995 – AMJ 2003	JFM 2003 – JFM 2006	OND 2005 – OND 2008
West	2.8±0.5	-13.9±1.5	4.6±0.7	12.6±1.0	-11.0±1.7
North-East	-0.5±0.3	1.0±0.8	1.1±0.3	-4.4±0.6	-1.4±0.7
South-East	-1.5±1.0	-19.6±3.5	-0.4±1.3	-6.2±2.4	-6.3±2.2

Table 6. Spatially averaged elevation change rates over three Greenland ice sheet areas and over different time periods.

Although radar altimetry does not allow investigating part of margin areas, ERS-1, 2 and Envisat measurements provide with comparatively long (from 1992 to present) elevation time series with high spatial and temporal resolution, which is sufficient for detailed investigation of Greenland ice sheet. Figure 17 shows elevation time series over three regions of the Greenland that are generally governed by different regional circulation regimes. These regions are separated by the ice divides outlined in the Figure 18 that shows spatial distributions of elevation change rates over different time periods. Western and south-eastern parts of Greenland, where accumulation is significantly influenced by Icelandic Low and Baffin Bay Low reveal the most significant inter-annual elevation changes, while over north-eastern area, which is located in a shadow of accumulation, only small seasonal variations are indicated. Largest elevation variability is indicated in the South-East area, where the largest precipitations and high ice sheet flow velocities are observed. Elevation time series before 1995 indicate strong elevation decreasing for both – west and

Figure 18. Elevation change rates derived by merging ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat satellite altimeter measurements when applying gradient $(\Delta dH / \Delta d\sigma^0)_{consecutive}$ (a) from AMJ 1992 to AMJ 1995 (b) from AMJ 1995 to AMJ 2003 (c) JFM 2003 to JFM 2006, and (d) from OND 2005 to OND 2008.

south-east – areas, but show remarkable difference for the period from 1995 (Fig.17 and 18, Table.6) Among the elevation variations over south-eastern area it can be noted two most pronounced features. First, sharp elevation increase by in 2002-2003 that is consistent with airborne laser altimeter measurements [Krabill et al., 2004] and caused by enhanced accumulation [Hanna et al., 2006]. Second, elevation decrease from the middle of 2005 to the end of 2006 is also in agreement with the results from model studies of accumulation in this area [Burgess et al., 2010]. Moderate ice sheet growth over western area from 1995 to 2003 changed to rapid elevation increase lasted till 2006, which is followed by the rapid elevation decrease. These changes on the west side of Greenland are also can be explained by relatively high and low modeled accumulation over Greenland in 2005 and 2006 respectively [Burgess et al., 2010].

Conclusions

Greenland ice sheet elevation changes for 16.5-year time period from 1992 to 2008 were analyzed from ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat satellite radar altimeter data. Continuous elevation and backscatter power time series were created through applying inter-satellite biases to crossover differences. Since biases are not spatially invariant over Greenland the method that utilizes amount of data sufficient to allow calculating bias for individual grid cells cell (1 degree longitude \times 0.5 degrees latitude) was developed. In addition inter-satellite biases have shown to be significantly effected by the bias between measurements in ascending and descending orbits. In order to take into account the ascending/descending bias available crossover differences between measurements from different satellites had to be split into two parts for calculation of two estimates for every bias. From the other side, the developed technique use the inter-satellite crossover differences with the possibly least time interval (dt) between measurements and takes into account temporal variations of elevation and backscatter power, when comparing measurement with large dt is necessary. The largest and smallest ERS-1/ERS-2 and ERS-2/Envisat elevation biases are observed over margins and in the central areas, respectively and vary over Greenland ice sheet from -1.8 to 3.4 m. Corresponding σ^0 biases are negative everywhere and are ranging from -9.8 to -1 dB.

Creating the time series for received backscatter power in addition to elevation time series was needed to determine correction, which takes into account relationship between these parameters. Detailed analysis of the correction revealed its essential dependence on temporal variations of the correlation gradient between elevation and backscattered power in addition to variations of backscattered power. In average over Greenland ice sheet relatively high and low gradients are observed before and after 2002 respectively. In addition, as gradients were calculated for parts of time series they are in average higher then the gradient determined from the whole time

series. Therefore adjusting elevation time series for correlation between elevation and backscattered power by applying variable gradient resulted in significant decline of elevation increase before 2003 reported previously. Comparison of elevation change rates derived from satellite radar altimeter data with those from laser altimetry over the same period of time indicates good agreement for high-elevation areas, where the coverage by laser and radar altimeter measurements are close. Whereas for the low-elevation regions below 2000 m, where thinning rates are highest, only 53% of the ice sheet are involved resulting in large discrepancy between the average values. We believe that adjusting elevation time series for correlation with backscattered power by applying variable gradients properly takes into account changes of the ice sheet scattering characteristics and is able to correct elevation change estimates for penetration of part of the radar altimeter signal through the surface.

Elevation change rate of 0.8 ± 0.3 cm/year over 76% of the Greenland ice sheet from 1992 to 2008 was found. Increases in surface elevation, which were observed over the high-elevation regions from 1995 have decelerated over the period from 2003 to 2005 and changed to elevation decrease during 2006-2008. In contrast, surface-elevation decreases from 2000 in the low-elevation areas of ice sheet have continued due to enhanced summer melting and especially pronounced in 2008. Over 87% of high-elevation areas above 1500 m elevation increase is 1.8 ± 0.2 cm/year. Elevation decrease with the rate -7.1 cm/year represents only 38% of areas below 1500 m, where amount of available crossovers are limited due to rougher sloping surface. Therefore involving more coastal areas would result in faster thinning than ~ 12 cm/year indicated from 2000.

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